

More inclusive meetings and networks, driving policy change and harnessing collective action

Report from Women in Crop Science coffee at the 2022 ASA, CSSA, and SSSA International Annual Meeting in Baltimore – 7th November, 2022

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The first Women in Crop Science coffee morning was held during the 2021 American Society of Agronomy (ASA), Crop Science Society of America (CSSA) and Soil Science Society of America (SSSA) International Annual Meeting in Salt Lake City in November 2021. This was an “experiment” to see if it was possible to better connect female scientists in an informal setting at one of the largest crop science meetings in the world. The event was a success and attendees reported that the coffee morning gave them the opportunity to connect and network with other scientists in a much more relaxed way and that it made attending the large event less daunting. Based on this feedback, and with the support of the ASA, CSSA and SSSA Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion committees and specifically the Women in Science committee we decided to run another event at the meeting in 2022 (<https://www.acsmmeetings.org/>). This built on a year of feedback and further development of Women in Crop Science community (<https://womenincropscience.org/>) including events at meetings (e.g. the 2022 Monogram UK meeting <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6511355>), internal discussions within our organizations (e.g. CIMMYT Kenya coffee morning <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6606887>) and Global Women in Crop Science coffee events held around the world during September, 2022 (summarized here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7213422>). The 2022 event was supported by Corteva, CIMMYT and Oklahoma State University. This report summarizes the event and the outcomes of the discussion topics.

Professor Roxana Savin gives an overview of her career journey (L) while attendees at the Women in Crop Science coffee morning in Baltimore are ready to discuss a range of topics (R)

Setting the scene: real-life stories from Women in Crop Science

The importance of sharing stories and experiences to foster better understanding and support is a central pillar of the Women in Crop Science community. For the Baltimore meeting we invited Professor Roxana Savin to share the journey of her career as well as challenges she has faced and advice for women working in crop sciences. Roxana is a Professor within the Department of Crop and Forest Sciences at The

University of Lleida in Spain. She is a leading expert in applied crop physiology working in multiple cereal species and with a specific focus on plant development under stress and implications of this for productivity and food security.

In her address Roxana highlighted the many positives of her career: the ability to work in interesting places with interesting people, to do work that you love and to train and support others to develop as scientists. She also shared her personal challenges including the difficulty of balancing work with family commitments, particularly with young children. Roxana gave an honest and open perspective on her experiences with balancing the many demands of academic life with having children and acknowledged that this remains a very large challenge to many females in crop science. She was also thankful for the support she received through this period from mentors and other leaders, highlighting the importance of having scientific and academic leaders who are aware of, and are willing to offer flexibility, to support women with family commitments.

Ensuring greater access to scientific networks: providing practical support at meetings

Following Roxana's address the attendees worked together to identify practical support that could be provided to make conferences and meetings more inclusive. Areas identified to specifically support parents of young children include ensuring the availability of specifically designated (and properly equipped) breastfeeding rooms, on-site or locally available childcare to allow parents to bring young children to meetings and the provision of childcare grants.

Further discussions highlighted the need for more informal networking at conferences, particularly large events that bring together hundreds or thousands of attendees. These situations can be very daunting for many people and it is a barrier to build relationships and professional networks in what still are seen as male-dominated situations. The attendees felt that the Women in Crop Science coffee was a great opportunity for networking and supported it becoming a regular part of the program. However, many suggested a longer session and/or a different format e.g. a mixer, full breakfast or lunch event. Participants most valued the opportunity to meet and connect with other women and suggested that future events could focus on transferable skills that are applicable across career stages.

All welcomed the opportunity to share knowledge across career stages and it was recommended that established women in the community could help to make introductions and facilitate networking for newer attendees. The need for wider reach was also highlighted, including the suggestion to include men, allies, and advocates as well as representatives of ASA, CSSA and SSSA society leadership at future events.

Challenges remain: providing a collective voice to drive change

In addition to the discussion of practical support at meetings, the presentation from Roxana sparked discussion of a number of other broader topics and challenges that still remain. The majority of the event participants are based in public sector organizations and universities in the US. Public sector science maternity leave policies remain a specific and major barrier to early and mid-career women with young children or who want to start a family. The opportunity to seek support from the ASA, CSSA and SSSA Policy group to address this issue collectively was strongly endorsed as it is a major driver of loss of female scientists from crop science and related fields.

The broader dynamics of crop science and related research fields were also discussed. These are still seen as being male-dominated, particularly at the current leadership level. Participants welcomed further discussion of and training in how to effectively speak up (and be heard) when witnessing a problem or challenge relating to gender equality. Changing the current expectation of authoritarian leadership style was also discussed, as was the continuing assumption of male vs. female behavior. At a practical level this still permeates in many organizations manifesting as distrust or doubt about the ability or willingness of females to do physical work or to be taken seriously when speaking up. Many women still feel that they do not have the space or security to say “no” and provide alternatives to male leaders or co-workers. The role and lessons of women in positions of authority should also be further supported as many still report being undermined, upwardly bullied or not taken as seriously as male equivalents.

Summary

Overall, the event highlighted the importance of networking events in bringing people together to connect, share ideas and support the collective. The group identified several practical ways to support women at meetings including specific recommendations for enabling the attendance of parents of young children. The discussions also highlighted many challenges which remain for the community and opportunities to rectify barriers that still exist for attracting, retaining and promoting gender diversity in our broad crop science community.

If you want to keep up-to-date with the latest Women in Crop Science community activities please join the Directory: <https://womenincropscience.org/directory/>